

EFFECTS OF ARTIFICIAL AGEING ON SEEDLING LENGTH (CM) OF SOYBEAN

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Abstract

The present investigation was undertaken at the Experimental Farm, Department of Agricultural Botany, VNMKV, Parbhani, Department of Soil Science and Agricultural Chemistry, VNMKV, Parbhani, Quality Control Laboratory, MSSC Ltd., Parbhani and Department of Soil Science and Agricultural Chemistry, College of Agriculture, Golegaon, Hingoli with soybean varieties viz: MAUS-71, MAUS-158, JS-335 and MAUS-162. The studies on effects of ageing revealed that, the seeds of all varieties (MAUS-71, MAUS-158, JS-335 and MAUS-162) were aged artificially at various time (24, 48, 72, 96 and 120 Hs.) and temperature (41^oc, 42^oc, 43^oc, 44^oc and 45^oc) variables. Soybean variety MAUS-162 was found to be better in respect of moisture percentage, germination, germination index, seedling length, seed vigour index and electrical conductivity as compared to MAUS-71, MAUS-158 and JS-335 at the end of 120 hrs. and 240 days of storage period. The soybean variety MAUS-162 was found to be better in respect of biochemical parameters i.e, malondialdehyde, superoxide dismutase, peroxide activity, protein, oil and dehydrogenase activity.

Keywords: soybean, ageing, temperature**Introduction**

Soybean [*Glycine max* (L.) Merrill] is an important oil crop in the family Leguminosae, subfamily Papilionaceae, and genus *Glycine* L. Soybean is of particular importance in times of energy crisis and closure and plays central role in agriculture, and export. It has now become an oil and seed crop and is the cheapest alternative source of high-quality protein and cooking oil. Soybeans are high in protein and a rich source of carbohydrates and fats. They are a good source of vitamins, minerals and beneficial plant compounds, such as isoflavones. Soybeans have great potential as a particularly nutritious and protein-rich food. In general, stronger seeds can withstand high temperatures and high humidity while producing normal seedlings. Field appearance and seed storage capacity are closely related to seed vigor, which in turn, is negatively affected by different aging periods and storage conditions. The quality of soybean seeds is easily degraded, making it difficult to preserve for a long time. The physiological properties and storage capacity of seeds are influenced by humidity, which in-turn is controlled by the relative humidity of the surrounding air. Seeds are hygroscopic, they tend to absorb or lose moisture causing various biochemical changes in soybeans.

Materials and Methods

The present investigation was carried out aiming at assessment of seed viability of plant species with high oil content and germination after seed had been stored and aged for certain period. Based on the aged seed vigor assessment, we can establish its field emergence capacity and possibility of forming vigorous and healthy plants which will be high yielding. The experimental material for the present investigation consists of four soybeans (*Glycine max* (L.) Merrill.) varieties representing two maturity groups viz., MAUS-71 and MAUS-158 (Early maturity group: 93-95 days) and JS-335 and MAUS-162 (Late maturity group: 95-103 days). The seed material was evaluated for different seed quality parameters under natural and accelerated ageing conditions. Seed quality parameters were judged at 0, 60, 120, 180 and 240 days of storage.

Results and Discussion**Table 1: Effect of artificial ageing on Seedling Length (cm) of soybean varieties**

V X T X H Mean Table

	V1=MAUS-71					V2=MAUS-158					V3=JS-335					V4=MAUS-162				
	T1	T2	T3	T4	T5	T1	T2	T3	T4	T5	T1	T2	T3	T4	T5	T1	T2	T3	T4	T5
H1	28.33	27.33	24.00	22.00	20.33	28.67	27.33	27.00	26.33	22.33	26.67	25.33	22.67	24.33	23.67	29.67	28.00	27.00	25.33	27.67
H2	27.33	24.67	22.33	17.33	16.67	27.33	27.00	22.33	24.33	20.67	24.67	23.67	20.67	17.33	20.33	29.33	26.33	25.67	24.33	25.00
H3	25.33	20.67	20.33	15.67	14.67	26.67	25.00	21.00	22.33	20.33	22.67	20.33	18.67	18.33	15.00	27.67	25.67	28.00	25.33	24.00
H4	20.67	17.67	17.67	12.67	10.67	22.33	22.00	19.33	17.67	13.67	20.33	18.00	14.33	14.67	12.00	25.00	23.67	23.67	22.67	21.67

The data on effect of varieties, temperature and storage hours on seedling length of soybean seed during artificial ageing are presented in Table 1 and Fig. 1

From the data, it was seen that the mean seedling length influenced significantly during all the storage periods of soybean varieties. It was also noticed that seedling length decreased with the advancement of storage period irrespective of varieties, temperature and storage hours. The significant differences in seedling length of varieties during all the storage periods were observed, irrespective of varieties, temperature and storage hours. At initial stage of storage, the mean seedling length of MAUS-162, MAUS-158, MAUS-71 and JS-335 was 29.66 cm, 28.66 cm, 28.33 cm and 26.66 cm, respectively.

The soybean variety MAUS-162 showed significantly higher (28.00 cm) seedling length than MAUS-158 (21.00 cm), MAUS-71 (20.33 cm) and JS-335 (18.66 cm) at AA for 72 hrs. and 43^oC temperature of storage periods and at the transition point for soybean storage period. Whereas, lower seedling length was observed when soybean varieties were stored at 45^oC temperature for 120 hrs in MAUS-71 (8.66 cm), MAUS-158 (10.00 cm) JS-335 (11.33 cm), and MAUS-162 (20.00 cm) respectively.

Seedling length decreased with increasing storage time. Seedling length decreased as storage time increased. Floris, (1970) reported that the decrease in soybean length could be due to ageing or deterioration of the seeds, which is a gradual process accompanied by the accumulation of metabolites, reducing the seedling growth and germination at a faster rate of senescence. As reported by Charjan and Tarar (1992), seedling length decreased with increasing storage time and relative humidity in soybean. Gregg (1982) reported that soybeans do not hold well at high humidity, storage hours and temperatures, but can be stored satisfactorily under controlled temperature and low temperature conditions. Razia Sultana *et al.*, (2016) also reported that showed maximum shoots and roots after 4 months of storage.

The seedling length was gradually decreased with subsequent increase in storage period under study.

H5	17.33	15.67	14.33	12.00	8.67	21.00	20.33	18.33	15.33	10.00	18.33	15.33	13.67	11.33	11.33	22.33	23.00	24.00	22.00	20.00
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Note V = Variety V1=MAUS-71 V2=MAUS-158, V3=JS-335, V4=MAUS-162
T = Temperature T1=41 °C, T2=42 °C, T3=43 °C, T4=44 °C, T5=45°C
H = Hours H1= 24hrs., H2= 48hrs., H3= 72hrs., H4= 96hrs., H5= 120 hrs.

VxT

	T1	T2	T3	T4	T5	Mean V
V1=MAUS-71	23.80	21.20	19.73	15.93	14.20	18.97
V2=MAUS-158	25.20	24.33	21.60	21.20	17.40	21.95
V3=JS-335	22.53	20.53	18.00	17.20	16.47	18.95
V4=MAUS-162	26.80	25.33	25.67	23.93	23.67	25.08
Mean T	24.58	22.85	21.25	19.57	17.93	

VxH

	H1	H2	H3	H4	H5	Mean V
V1=MAUS-71	24.40	21.67	19.33	15.87	13.60	18.97
V2=MAUS-158	26.33	24.33	23.07	19.00	17.00	21.95
V3=JS-335	24.53	21.33	19.00	15.87	14.00	18.95
V4=MAUS-162	27.53	26.13	26.13	23.33	22.27	25.08
Mean H	25.70	23.37	21.88	18.52	16.72	

TxH

	H1	H2	H3	H4	H5	Mean T
T1	28.33	27.17	25.58	22.08	19.75	24.58
T2	27.00	25.42	22.92	20.33	18.58	22.85
T3	25.17	22.75	22.00	18.75	17.58	21.25
T4	24.50	20.83	20.42	16.92	15.17	19.57
T5	23.50	20.67	18.50	14.50	12.50	17.93
Mean H	25.70	23.37	21.88	18.52	16.72	

Note V = Variety V1=MAUS-71 V2=MAUS-158, V3=JS-335, V4=MAUS-162
T = Temperature T1=41 °C, T2=42 °C, T3=43 °C, T4=44 °C, T5=45°C
H = Hours H1=24hrs., H2=48hrs., H3=72hrs., H4=96hrs., H5=120 hrs.

TABLE OF SEM, SED AND C.D.

Factors	C.D.	SE(d)	SE(m)
Factor(V)	0.21	0.10	0.07
Factor(T)	0.23	0.12	0.08
Interaction V X T	0.46	0.23	0.17
Factor(H)	0.23	0.12	0.08
Interaction V X H	0.46	0.23	0.17
Interaction T X H	0.51	0.26	0.18
Interaction V X T X H	1.03	0.52	0.37

Note: V = Variety V1=MAUS-71 V2=MAUS-158, V3=JS-335, V4=MAUS-162
T = Temperature T1=41 °C, T2=42 °C, T3=43 °C, T4=44 °C, T5=45°C
H = Hours H1=24hrs., H2=48hrs., H3=72hrs., H4=96hrs., H5=120 hrs.

Fig. 1: Effect of artificial ageing on Seedling Length (cm) of soybean varieties

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